

ASSESSING THE INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL PAYMENTS SYSTEMS ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN PETROLEUM RETAIL OUTLETS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT: In an increasingly cashless economy, digital payment systems have become essential for enhancing service delivery in retail sectors, including petroleum retail outlets. In Nigeria, particularly in Akwa Ibom State, the adoption of digital payment platforms such as POS, mobile transfers and USSD codes has reshaped how customers interact with fuel service providers. As customer expectations for speed, reliability and convenience grow, the performance of these digital systems plays a critical role in shaping satisfaction levels. The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of digital payments systems on customer satisfaction of the petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, the main source of data was through primary source with the use of questionnaire. The researcher adopted the survey research design approach and data were collected from 323 respondents drawn from the petroleum firms' customers' base. A total number of 317 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved in useable form representing 98.1 percent of data analyzed using the Simple Regression Model (SRM). Data generated from the study were processed using descriptive and inferential statistics and hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that digital payments systems had significant influence on customer satisfaction of the petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, the study recommended that petroleum marketers in the state should Offer a range of accessible payment methods including POS, USSD, mobile transfers, QR codes and digital wallets to accommodate customer preferences. They should also keep payment systems functional during both peak and off-peak hours to avoid service delays.

Keywords: Digital Payments Systems, Payments Systems Reliability, Payments Systems Accessibility, Customer Satisfaction.

Introduction

The rapid evolution of digital payment systems has significantly transformed the landscape of financial transactions globally, with Nigeria being no exception. In recent years, the adoption of digital payment methods such as point of sale (POS) terminals, mobile wallets and bank transfers has surged, particularly within the petroleum retail sector. This shift is driven by the need for more efficient, secure and convenient payments solutions that cater to the dynamic demands of consumers (Chukwu, et al., 2021).

In Nigeria, the proliferation of fintech solutions like OPay, PalmPay and moniepoint has facilitated seamless transactions, enabling customers to make payments swiftly and securely at fuel stations. According to a mastercard survey, 96% of Nigerian consumers are considering emerging payment methods, with 81% expressing increased loyalty to retailers offering multiple payment options. This trend underscores the growing importance of digital payment systems in enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty (Agrawal and Verma, 2024).

However, despite the evident benefits, challenges persist in the implementation of digital payment systems within Nigeria's retail outlets. Issues such as network instability, transaction failures and limited infrastructures have been reported, hindering seamless execution of digital transactions. These challenges not only affect the efficiency of payment processes but also impact customer satisfaction negatively.

Given the critical role of customer satisfaction in the success of retail businesses, it is imperative to assess the influence of digital payment systems on customer experiences. This study aims to evaluate how the adoption and implementation of digital payment methods affect customer satisfaction in Nigeria's petroleum retail outlets. By identifying the benefits and challenges associated with digital payments, the research seeks to provide insights that can inform strategies for enhancing customer satisfaction and optimizing payments processes in the sectors.

Statement of the Problem

The adoption of digital payment systems in Nigeria has gained momentum, particularly in response to the cashless policy promoted by the central bank of Nigeria and the expansion of fintech services in the petroleum retail sector, the integration of digital payment options such as mobile transfers, POS terminals and payment apps is intended to enhance operational efficiency, reduce cash handling and improve customer experience. However, persistent challenges such as poor network connectivity, transaction failures, delays in confirmation and lack of trust in electronic payment infrastructure continue to hinder the effective utilization of these systems.

Despite widespread availability, many customers still express dissatisfaction with their digital payment experiences at fuel stations. This dissatisfaction not only undermines customer loyalty but also threatens the competitive positioning of petroleum retailers in an increasingly digital economy. Existing research has explored digital payments in general retail and banking but there is limited empirical evidence specifically examining how these systems influence customer satisfaction within petroleum retail outlets, especially in the unique context of Nigeria's infrastructural and technological limitations.

Therefore, there is a critical need to assess the influence of digital payment systems on customer satisfaction in petroleum retail outlets in Nigeria. This research seeks to fill that gap by identifying key factors of digital payment systems and evaluating their impact on customer perceptions, trust and repeat patronage.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of digital payment systems on customer satisfaction in petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The specific objectives therefore include to:

- Examine the influence of payment systems reliability on customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- Ascertain how payment system accessibility influences customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study attempt to provide answers to the following research questions:

- What is the influence of payment systems reliability on customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- To what extent does payment system accessibility influence customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses where postulated to guide the study

Ho₁: Payment systems reliability does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: Payment system accessibility does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of petroleum downstream retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Digital Payment Systems

Digital payment systems have been defined in various ways by different authors and institutions. Hidayanto et al. (2015) defined e-payment as any prevailing or new payment system that enables financial transactions to be conducted safely from one organization or individual to another via the internet. Effah (2016) describe online payment as the exchange of monetary value between payers and payees via the internet. Gupta et al. (2020) sees it as a method of payment which can be made by the use of banking cards, USSD, AEPS, e-wallets, UPI, etc. Both payer and payee use digital mode to send and receive money.

Security is paramount in digital payment systems, directly influencing customer trust and satisfaction. A systematic review highlights robust encryption and multi-factor authentications are critical in protecting sensitive information, thereby enhancing customer confidence and fostering loyalty (Sivathanu, 2019).

The convenience offered by digital payment platforms such as user-friendly interfaces, multiple payments options and quick transaction processes significantly improves the overall shopping experience. This ease of use is a key determinant of customer satisfaction.

Digital payment systems have revolutionized commerce especially in emerging economies, by offering convenient, secure and faster mode of transactions. This shift has significantly influence consumer behavior, leading to increased spending tendencies when using digital payment systems compared to cash transactions (Bisma et al., 2020).

Payment Systems Reliability and Customer Satisfaction

The reliability of digital payments systems is paramount in Nigerian petroleum retail sector. Frequent transactions failures, delayed confirmations and network issues have been reported, leading to customer dissatisfaction. The independent petroleum marketers association of Nigeria (IPMAN) highlighted that poor bank networks and transaction glitches are frustrating the use of electronic payment in petrol stations, causing delays and eroding customer trust (Shehu and Bardi, 2024).

Unreliable payment systems directly affect customer satisfaction. Instances of double debits, delayed transaction alerts and lack of immediate transaction confirmations have been reported by customers, leading to frustration

and a lack of confidence in digital payments methods. Such experiences can deter customers from using electronic payment options, preferring cash transactions instead (Nwidua, 2025).

Due to concerns over reliability, customers show a preference for payment methods that are less dependent on internet connectivity. Study focusing on SMEs in Nigeria's retail sector found that Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) transactions were preferred by 30% of respondents, as they offer more reliable and instantaneous transactions confirmations compared to other digital payments methods.

Point of sale (POS) systems, while widely accepted has their own set of reliability issues. Network failures, transaction errors and security concerns have been reported affecting customer trust and satisfaction. Additionally, there are concerns about cyber security threats associated with POS kiosks, including card cloning and unauthorized access, which further erode customer confidence in these systems.

Payment System Accessibility and Customer Satisfaction

The payment system accessibility refers to the ease with which consumers can use and benefit from various payment platforms such as POS, mobile banking or e-wallets without facing technical, geographic, physical or financial barriers. Ojo (2022) defined it as the degree to which users can conveniently initiate, process and complete financial transactions using available payments channels, regardless of their location or technological capability. Central Bank of Nigeria (2020) framed accessibility as a component of financial inclusion focusing on the ability of individuals and businesses to access payment services without discrimination or technological constraint.

Digital accessibility including the availability of technological services and good internet facilities is a critical factor influencing customer satisfaction in the petroleum industry. A study on customers' perception of service quality at NNPC retail outlets in Enugu urban identified services comprising technological services and good internet facilities as the factor with the highest mean score indicating a strong appreciation for these services among customers. This underscores the importance of digital accessibility in enhancing customer satisfaction.

The adoption of self-service technologies (SSTs) in fuel stations has been shown to positively impact customer engagement. Anka and Shamin (2025) found that customer willingness to use SSTs correlates positively with customer trust and intimacy. The study suggests that implementing SSTs can enhance customer satisfaction by fostering trust and reducing corruption at fuel stations.

Customer Satisfaction

Kotler and Keller (2016) defined customer satisfaction as a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance or outcome to his or her expectation. Homburg, Koschate and Hoyer (2006) describe it as an overall evaluation based on the total purchase and consumption experience with a good or service over time.

Etuk and Awah (2025) sees customer satisfaction as a pivotal factor influencing customer loyalty, repeat business and overall profitability. They defined it as the degree to which customers expectations are met or exceeded encompassing aspects such as product and service quality.

The integration of digital payments options has been linked to improved customer satisfaction. A study focusing on SMEs in Nigeria's retail sector found that the adoption of digital payment methods, such as USSD and POS, significantly enhanced customer experience. Customer favoured payment methods that were reliable and did not

depend heavily on internet connectivity. Usoro and Etuk (2023) observed that perceived usefulness of USSD and POS in fuel stations directly influenced satisfaction levels due to faster service and fewer errors.

Theoretical Framework

In this section the theory considered relevant for this study was;

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) propounded by Fred Davis (1986)

This is one of the most widely used models in understanding how users come to accept and use technology. It was developed to explain and predict users' acceptance of new technologies. The model proposes that two major factors influence a person decision to adopt and use technology:

- Perceived usefulness (PU): The degree to which a person believes that using a particular technology will enhance their performance or make a task easier.
- Perceived ease of use (PEOU): The degree to which a person believes that using the technology will be free of effort.

TAM suggests that when people perceive a technology as useful and easy to use, they are more likely to accept and adopt it. This model has been widely applied in studying technology use across various sectors, including marketing and consumer behavior.

TAM has been widely applied to digital payment adoption. In Nigeria's petroleum sector, customers increasingly interact with technologies like POS, mobile wallets, USSD and online banking. They are more likely to adopt them and feel satisfied with the service.

Review of Empirical Studies

Nwidua (2025): Electronic payment systems and customer patronage of shopping malls in south-south zone, Nigeria. The study aimed to explore the relationship between electronic payment systems and customer patronage of shopping mall. The method involved a descriptive survey research method. The finding of the study revealed that card payment system, electronic funds transfer and e-wallet payment system had a significant relationship with customer patronage of shopping malls in south-south zone, Nigeria. They recommended that shopping mall operators in the zone who were yet to introduce sustainable electronic payment system should introduce it immediately to promote customer patronage and repeat purchase.

Shehu and Bardi (2024): Evaluating the impact of electronic payment systems on service delivery: A case study of Warri refining petroleum company. The main objective of the study was to investigate the impact of electronic payment systems on service delivery at Warri refining petroleum company (WRPC). The method involved analyzing survey data using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that e-payment systems significantly influenced service delivery of Warri refining Petroleum Company. They recommended that the company should invest in technology and increase customer education to optimize the benefits of electronic payments in the oil and gas industry.

Akpan, Awah and Mfon (2024): The Moderating Role of Age and Education in the relationship between E-Service ease of use and Customer Loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria. The study aimed to examine the moderating effects of age and education on the relationship between e-service ease-of-use and customer loyalty among online shoppers in Nigeria. The method of data analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that ease-of-use alone accounts for 1.7% of the variation in customer loyalty. Hence,

when age was introduced as a moderating variable, the explained variance increased significantly to 30.9%, highlighting its substantial moderating effect. They recommended that online retailers should tailor their platforms to meet the specific needs of different age groups and educational backgrounds to enhance customer satisfaction and retention.

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study

The researcher employed a survey research design for this study. Data on both the independent variable and the dependent variable were gathered from various petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This design enabled the researcher to effectively engage with a significant number of the petroleum retail outlets customers in the region.

Population of the Study

The study's target population included all petroleum retail outlet customers in Akwa Ibom State, making the Population effectively limitless.

Sampling and the Sample Size determination

Since the population size for the study was infinite, sample size for this study was determined using the Topman Formula at 5% level of tolerable error.

The formula is given as

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$

Where n = required sample size

z = the value of z-score associated with the degree of confidence is 95% confidence level being 1.96 from the Z-score table.

p = 0.7 decimal (positive)

q = 0.3 decimal (negative)

e = acceptable tolerance level of error (stated in percentage points)

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$
$$= \frac{1.96^2 \cdot (0.7 \times 0.3)}{0.05^2}$$

$$= \frac{3.8416 \times 0.21}{0.0025}$$

$$= \frac{0.806736}{0.0025}$$

$$= 322.6$$

$$= 323$$

Therefore, the sample size of the study was 323.

Sampling Procedure

The study utilized a convenient sampling method for administering the research instrument. This approach involved contacting respondents based on their willingness to take part in the research, as well as their accessibility and availability to the researcher.

Methods of Data Collection

The data analysis included both descriptive and inferential statistics. A simple regression analysis was conducted to assess how digital payment systems influenced customer satisfaction. All hypotheses were tested at a significance level of $P > 0.05$.

Sources of Data

The main source of data employed in this study was the primary data source. The primary data source was a structured questionnaire which was served on respondents. The questionnaire was made up of two sections: section “A” generated data on demography, while section “B” was made up of two sub- sections which were the independent variable (digital payment systems) and the dependent variable (customer satisfaction).

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data Analysis

Test of Hypothesis One

Payment systems reliability does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Model Summary of the Influence of Payment Systems Reliability on Customer Satisfaction of Petroleum Retail Outlets

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std.Error of the Estimate
1	.827 ^a	.875	.794	.81730

a. Predictors (constant), Payment Systems Reliability

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Analysis of Variance of the Influence of Payment Systems Reliability on Customer Satisfaction of Petroleum Retail Outlets

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	1843.732	1	1748.957	2572.813	.000 ^b
1 Residual	741.582	316	6.943		
Total	2585.314	317			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Customer Satisfaction

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), Payment Systems Reliability

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The regression in table 1 shows that the coefficient of the constant terms (that is, the explanatory or predictor) variable. Payment Systems Reliability has R-value of (.827) which indicates a positive relationship

between the explanatory variable and the criteria variable. The R-square, the coefficient of determination value is (.875). This means that 87.5 percent of the variation on the Customer Satisfaction can be explained from the independent variable (Payment Systems Reliability). The table also shows the adjusted R-square for the model as (.794). But adjusted R-square is very useful in multiple regression analysis where it adjusts the R-square by the number of predictor values in the model. This adjustment allows the easy comparison of the explanatory power of the models with different numbers of independent variables. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table shows the overall regression effect in the model. The F-ratio value is 2585.314 which is significant at 0.000 and is less than 0.05 percent level of significance. Therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept that Payment Systems Reliability contribute towards Customer Satisfaction of Petroleum Retail Outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

.Hypothesis 2

Payment system accessibility does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Model Summary of Payment Systems Accessibility on Customer Satisfaction of Petroleum Retail Outlets

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.748	.857	.813	.57391

a. Predictors: (Constant), Payment system accessibility

Analysis of Variance of the Influence of Payment Systems Accessibility on Customer Satisfaction of Petroleum Retail Outlets

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	1945.821	1	1693.971	2462.641	.000 ^b
1 Residual	824.869	316	5.621		
Total	2770.690	317			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Customer Satisfaction

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), Payment system accessibility

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The regression result in table 2 revealed that the regression coefficient of R-value is (.748) which indicates that there is a strong positive relationship existing between Payment system accessibility and Customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets. The model summary table shows that the R-Square regression coefficient is (.857), which indicate that Payment system accessibility accounts for 85.7 percent of the total variation on the Customer Satisfaction of the petroleum retail outlets in the study area. The ANOVA table shows the F-ratio for the regression model which indicates the statistical significance of the overall regression model. The F-ratio value is 2462.641 which is statistically significance at 0.000 level, since the probability value (P-V=0.000) is less than 0.05 percent, we reject the null hypothesis and upheld the alternative. This means that there is a significant influence of Payment system accessibility on Customer Satisfaction in the petroleum retail outlets.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis of this study states that Payment systems reliability does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed a significant influence of Payment systems reliability on customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table 1 shows the overall regression effect in the model. The F-ratio was 2585.314 which was significant at 0.000 and was less than 0.05 percent level of significance. This is in consonance with the study of Nwidua (2025) who found out that there was a significant influence of electronic payment systems on customer patronage of shopping malls in south-south zone, Nigeria.

The second hypothesis of this study states that Payment systems accessibility does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed a significant influence of Payment systems accessibility on customer satisfaction of petroleum retail outlets. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table 2 shows the overall regression effect in the model. The F-ratio was 2462.641 which was significant at 0.000 and was less than 0.05 percent level of significance. This is in consonance with the study of Shehu and Bardi (2024) which revealed that electronic payment systems significantly influenced service delivery of Warri refining Petroleum Company.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

The main thrust of this study has been presented in the preceding sections. This section is concerned with the summary of major findings. The study investigated the influence of digital payment systems on customer satisfaction in the Nigerian petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Two hypotheses were formulated to guide this study and all the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance through the use of simple regression analysis. The two null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted. This resulted from the fact that the regression results were all significant, the computed F-values for all the two hypotheses show statistical significance of the overall regression model, this means that there was statistical significant influence of Digital Payment Systems Strategies such as (Payment Systems Reliability and Payment Systems Accessibility) on Customer Satisfaction in the Nigerian petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

To achieve the objectives, a survey research design was used to reach out to the respondents of the petrol firms. The population of the study was infinite. The Topman sample size determination formula at 5% level of tolerable error was used to determine the sample size of 323. The convenience sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for the study.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were established.

- Payment Systems Reliability has significant influence on customer Satisfaction in the Nigerian petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- Payment Systems Accessibility has significant influence on customer Satisfaction in the Nigerian petroleum retail outlets in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, we recommend that petroleum marketers in the state should:

- Collaborate with reputable banks and fintech firms that offer secure and stable transaction systems, maintain reliable POS terminals and mobile payments platforms to prevent transactions failures.
- Offer a range of accessible payment methods including POS, USSD, mobile transfers, QR codes and digital wallets to accommodate customer preferences. They should also keep payment systems functional during both peak and off-peak hours to avoid service delays.

REFERENCES

- Agodi, J. E., Aniekan E. A., and Oladipupo, A. (2016). Determinants of customers' patronage of fast food restaurants in Umuhia, Abia State, Nigeria; *Journal of Economic Research and Entrepreneurship Development*. ISSN 9876- 5432:vol. 2, No. 2.
- Agodi, J. E., Ahaiwe, E. O., Awah, A. E. (2017). Salesman's personality Trait and its Effects on sales performance: Study of Fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) in Abia State, Nigeria, *international Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* Vol. 8, No. 24.
- Agodi, J.E., Kalu, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2021). Impact of service recovery on customer loyalty of selected SMEs in Abia State, Nigeria, *journal of Business Administration and Management Science*, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, 1(1), 143-150
- Akpan, A. B. and Abdul, Z.(2009). Assessment of the impact of the of automated teller machine (ATM) on customer satisfaction the Nigerian banking industry, *Academy International journal of Nigeria*, International headquarters, Ahmadu Bello university,Zaria,Nigeria,1(1),64-76.
- Akpan, A. B.(2007). Effective of bank capitalization and confidence: An assessment of customers perception in Nigeria, *Abuja journal of business administration*, University of Abuja,Nigeria,1(2),96-110.
- Attih., O., Ikpe, I. and Mfon, A. (2017). Service marketing: A review. Akwa. Ibom. State. University (Aksu) *journal of management sciences*, 2(1),19-22.
- Attih, O. B. (2020). Packaging attributes and consumer patronage of beverages in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *British journal of marketing studies*, 8(6), 1-18.
- Awah, A.E., Mfon, A. A and Ibok, N.I. (2024). Celebrity endorsement and consumer buying behavior of Generation Y: A case study of select betting business in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. *Advance Journal of Economics*, 9(1), 1-14

- Awah, A. E., Akpan, A. O. and Emmanuel, D. O. (2024). Service quality dimension and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Advance Journal of Economics and Marketing Research*,9(2), 2-22.
- Awah, A. E., Akpan, A. O. and Emmanuel, D. O. (2024). Responsiveness and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Research Journal of Marketing and Allied Studies*,12(1), 42-58.
- Awah A. E. (2015). Insurance Marketing in Tropical Issues in Marketing Vol. I.P. 198-213.
- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Eno, N.A. (2021). Pull promotion in the marketing of bank services: among microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, *Advance Journal of Economics and Marketing Research*, 4(9), 1-15
- Awah, A.E, Akpan, A.O. and Sampson, E.A. (2021). Public relations and savings mobilizations drive of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Advance.Journal of Economic and Marketing Research*, 6(7), 11-16
- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Ele, L.E. (2021). Personal selling and saving mobilization drive of Uniuoyo Microfinance bank. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Marketing*, 11(10), 1-9.
- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Mfon, A.A . (2024). An analytical study on the influence of brand associations on customer patronage of smart phones in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria: A consumer behavior perspective, *British international journal of business and marketing research*, 7(6), 21-37.
- Edem, U. E. & Bassey, A. I. (2022). Content marketing strategies and customer loyalty among fuel retailers in Akwa Ibom S tate. *Journal of strategic marketing in Africa*, 4(2), 29-41.
- Effiong, M. J. & Udo, I.E. (2023). Digital communication and consumer behavior in the Nigeria oil sector. *Journal of marketing innovation*,1 1(2),44-57.
- Etuk, A., Awah, E.A. and Akpan O.A. (2020). E-Markting and savings mobilization drive of selected Microfinanace banks in UyO metrolopolis, Akwa Ibom state. *An international journal of Business Marketing and Management*.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2022). Factors influencing the adoption of mobile apps among young people in Nigeria. A study of University of Uyo students, *European Journal of Business and Management*, 14(3), 65-73
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2022). E-marketing Strategies and savings mobilization drive of selected microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, *International Journal of Business, Marketing and Management*, 7(3), 1-6

- Etuk, S.G., Udo I.S. and Awah A. (2022), Customer relationship management and marketing technology, *Strategic Marketing Communication Consult*
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A.E. (2023). Electronic banking and marketing performance of deposit money banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. *American Interdisciplinary Journal of Business and Economics (AIJBE)*, 10(3), 23-42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8346738>
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Physical ambience and Customer behavior in selected microfinance banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, *Top American Journal of marketing*, 9(1), 1-24.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A. E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Assurance and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *American journal of information technology and management*, 12(2), 1-23.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). E-service reliability and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education, *Journal of current research in business and management sciences*, 12(2), 2-16.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Empathy and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Marketing Research and Brand Management*, 12(2), 36-50.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). The role of age and education in moderating the relationship between e-service security and customer loyalty: The Nigerian online shopping experience, *Michigan International Journal of Marketing. New Media and Communication*, 12(2), 50-64.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A. E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Tangibility and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Business and Cooperative Research*, 9(2), 1-19.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). E- Service responsiveness and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education, *European Journal of Marketing and Management Sciences*, 7(2), 13-30.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Internal marketing strategies and employee performance of commercial banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, *American research journal of economics, finance and management*, 12 (3), 47-65
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). E-Service fulfillment and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education, *British international journal of business and marketing research*, 7(4), 41-59.

- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Marketing communication and consumer behaviour of betting firms in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *Advanced journal of economics and business research*, 12(3), 17-34.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). Digital transformation service marketing in Nigeria; Reshaping strategies and enhancing customer engagement, *Michigan journal of multidisciplinary research*, 12(3), 29-45.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). An empirical analysis of customer complaint management systems and their influence on customer satisfaction in the smart phone Industry: A case study of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *International journal of management communication*, 12(4), 1-15.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). Advertising budgets and financial performance: Analysing the optimal balance for long-term profitability in Nigerian startups, *American interdisciplinary journal of business and economics*, 11(4), 18-30.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2025). The role of mobile apps in enhancing service marketing effectiveness in Nigeria's financial service sector, *Holex journal of marketing and mass communication*, 13(1), 17-28.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2025). Analysis of the influence of Ai-driven services on customer perception in the Nigerian e-commerce sector, *International journal of interdisciplinary research in marketing and management*, 12(1), 1-16.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2025). Analyzing customer perception and customer satisfaction in the hospitality sector: Insights from hotels in Akwa Ibom State, *Research journal of marketing and allied studies*, 13(1), 13-25.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2025). The influence of online reviews on brand perception and customer engagement in service marketing in Nigeria, *International journal of contemporary research in marketing and management sciences*. 13(1), 1-14.
- Etuk, A., & Awah, A. E. (2025). The role of technological service innovation in enhancing customer satisfaction: An IoT and smart hospitality study of hotels in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. *International journal of interdisciplinary research in marketing and management*, 12(1), 16-28.
- Kim, J. and Kim, W.G. (2021). Effect of hotel service quality and satisfaction on customer loyalty, *Journal of hospitality and tourism research*, 45(3), 428-450.

- Lee, Y. and Cheng, T. (2021). The impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the hotel industry, *International journal of hospitality management*,95(10,)29-48
- Nwachukwu, C. & Okoro, G. (2023). Adoption of digital marketing in Nigeria's petroleum downstream sector: Opportunities and constraints. *African journal of business and digital economy*,5(1), 21-35.
- Obong, J. A. & Ekanem, E. U.(2022). Social media usage and marketing effectiveness among SME's in Akwa Ibom State. *Nigerian journal of digital marketing*, 8(1), 13-28.
- Pulizzi, J. & Rose, R. (2022). *Killing marketing: How innovative businesses are turning marketing cost into profit*, McGraw-Hill.
- Udonde, U.E, Akpan, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2022). Internal marketing and employee performance in insurance industry in Nigeria, *British, International Journal of Business and Marketing Research*, 5(1), 1-22.
- Udonde, U.E., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2022). Effect of communication and empowerment on sales-force performance in the Nigerian insurance industry. *Advance Journal of Economic and Marketing Research*, 7(11).
- Udoh, I.S., Jospeh, U.E. and Awah, A. (2022). Service Experience and passengers' patronage of transit companies in the south-south region of Nigeria. *British Journal*.